

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Optimized Grid Voxelization for Obstacle Avoidance in Collaborative Robotics

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ABSTRACT Voxelization into a fixed voxel grid is used for simplicity of processing and data format for applications such as dynamic re-planning of a collaborative robot path around a dynamic obstacle. In this case, it may be undesirable that conventional voxelization methods generate more volume, which results in a longer generated path than needed if the real shape of the obstacle was used instead of voxels. The approach proposed in this paper utilizes triangular normals of the mesh formed by neighboring points in a depth image to adjust the occupancy of a fixed voxel grid, ensuring the voxels more accurately represent the true volume of the scanned object. An experiment with real hardware was performed to compare the proposed voxelization method with the conventional fixed grid voxelization method. The collected point clouds are voxelized using both methods, and the resulting voxel maps are then passed to a simple path solver to find the length of the robot path around the obstacle. The results indicate that our proposed method achieves better results in terms of shorter avoidance paths, as our method provides a tighter representation of the obstacle. The average increase in the length of the alternative avoidance path compared to the theoretical shortest path around the object was 15.7 % for the conventional method and 8.6 % for the presented method. Overall, the experimental results indicate the usefulness of the developed system, as it can shorten the robot cycle time when avoiding obstacles.

INDEX TERMS Fixed grid, robot workspace monitoring, voxel, voxelization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of collaborative robotics has introduced the possibility of sharing a workspace between robots and humans, enabling the combination of their respective strengths to enhance efficiency and reduce the time required to complete tasks [1]. However, with the development of collaborative applications, it has become evident that in certain cases, robots are stopped to prevent potential collisions with workers (for safety reasons) [2]. These collisions have various causes, but can generally be attributed to a mutual misun-

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derstanding of intentions between the robot and the human. Recent advances in application development have focused on creating systems that aim to prevent this misunderstanding. There are categories of systems that inform human workers about the intentions of the robot through visual, auditory, and haptic feedback [3], [4], [5]. Additionally, there are systems designed to inform the robot about the worker's intentions. Using monitoring technologies, these systems enable the robot to respond immediately to the operator's movements by halting its activity or re-planning its trajectory [6]. A key aspect of developing the aforementioned systems is the precise and efficient monitoring of the collaborative workspace. A well-designed monitoring system must enable

accurate real-time object detection, ensure full coverage of the collaborative area, and efficiently transmit the collected information to the supervisory system [7].

Depth sensors are widely used to monitor the environment of collaborative robots [8], [9]. These cameras provide real-time depth images that can be projected into 3D space to create a point cloud. Point clouds allow for precise representation of the shape and details of objects, making them highly desirable for monitoring collaborative workspaces. They are widely utilized for object detection, segmentation, and recognition in robotics, as highlighted in numerous review studies [11], [12], [13], [14]. Working with raw point clouds, both in the general and in the context of collaborative robotics, presents challenges that need to be addressed. Raw point clouds consist of unorganized 3D points without known neighborhood relationships. The density of points obtained from depth sensors depends on their distance from the sensor, resulting in variable coordinate accuracy. When data comes from multiple sources, overlapping areas create redundant points. In addition, point clouds contain noise caused by the physical limitations of sensors and inconsistencies during acquisition, such as poor lighting conditions. This noise complicates distinguishing fine details from noise, as relationships between neighboring points are not defined [15], [16].

Denoising point clouds can be addressed using various approaches. One common method employs the Moving Least Squares technique, which approximates an underlying surface and projects noisy points onto this surface, thus improving the quality of the representation [17], [18]. Other approaches, based on Sparse Representations, focus on reconstructing smooth surfaces by using sparse transitions between regions with varying point densities [19], [20], [21]. Methods utilizing non-local self-similarity exploit similarities between distant surfaces and utilize various representations (e.g., polynomial surfaces or point normals) to achieve smoother surfaces and effectively remove noise [22], [23], [24]. Geometric deep learning offers an advanced approach designed to preserve fine details, including sharp edges. Specialized methods for detecting sharp features utilize clean normal fields and selective feature detection algorithms, preventing point clustering and the formation of gaps in regions with sharp edges [16]. The application of these methods for real-time point cloud processing is computationally intensive. Accessing specific points from large discrete datasets is challenging, which can pose issues for real-time monitoring of a robot's workspace. For this reason, targeted downsampling techniques are increasingly employed to simplify data and enhance processing efficiency without significant loss of critical information. There is a wide variety of point cloud downsampling methods, which can be categorized into deep learning-based methods, grid-based methods, clustering methods, and voxel-based downsampling [25].

In the field of collaborative robot workspace monitoring, voxel representation of points is commonly used [26],

[27], [28]. Voxels provide an efficient 3D representation of space using a regular grid, where each cell indicates whether the space is occupied. This approach is simpler to process than point clouds and enables robotic systems to quickly analyze and identify obstacles, which is crucial for dynamic path replanning. Unlike point clouds, which require high computational power, voxel grids compress space into a structured format, facilitating real-time operations. In addition, by adjusting the voxel size, the ratio between detail and computational requirements can be adjusted.

Voxelization can be performed in several ways as described in review articles [15], [29]. The simplest way to voxelize a point cloud is fixed voxelization. The method consists of converting the point cloud into a fixed grid of voxels of a fixed size. The advantage of this method is its fast and computationally efficient simple implementation. It is suitable for applications with limited computational resources or for real-time computations [7]. A fixed voxel size can lead to inaccuracies in objects with varying granularity or in areas with high point density. At low resolutions, there is a risk of losing details. An alternative approach is adaptive voxelization, where the voxel size dynamically adjusts based on point density or distance from the sensor. This method allows for more accurate representation of complex shapes and optimizes memory usage [30]. However, its drawback is higher computational complexity due to the dynamic voxel adjustments, making it less suitable for real-time applications. The voxelization of a point cloud containing noise can be problematic, where outlying points can cause a miscast voxel that can create a phantom obstacle and significantly affect the robot's avoidance path. For this purpose voxelization approach based on Statistical Outlier Removal (SOR) is commonly used. This method preprocesses the data and involves removing points that deviate significantly from neighbouring values, thereby reducing the effect of noise. It enhances the quality of the voxel representation by eliminating outlier points that could distort results. However, a potential downside is the removal of some useful data, particularly in sparse point clouds [31]. There are methods of probabilistic voxelization, where voxel occupancy is not interpreted in a binary value (occupied vs. unoccupied) but is expressed as a probability of occupancy. This approach is well-suited for applications in high-noise environments, such as those with poor lighting conditions or when using less accurate sensors. Another category is voxelization using deformable voxel structures, where the voxel grid and the voxels themselves adapt to the shape and orientation of the captured objects. This enables a more accurate representation of the geometric features of surfaces by conforming the voxel structure to the object's contours [15]. The disadvantage of this method is its complex implementation and very high computational complexity, which makes it unsuitable for real-time processing.

In previously published works focused on designing a system for dynamic obstacle avoidance, we employed a

custom implementation of point cloud downsampling [6], [7]. Specifically, voxel filtering was utilized, which involves dividing the space into a regular grid (voxels) and replacing the points assigned to a specific voxel with its centroid. Using a fixed voxel grid with predefined boundaries and voxel size allows for precise determination of the maximum possible number of voxels in the voxel map. This allows the position of a voxel to be reconstructed from a simple integral unique identifier (voxel index). It also significantly simplifies and speeds up algorithms that work with the data. To eliminate noise, a post-processing filter is implemented based on a probabilistic outlier removal approach. This filter determines whether a voxel represents noise or an actual object surface by evaluating the density of points within the voxel. For effective dynamic obstacle avoidance by the robot, it is crucial to ensure that the volume represented by the voxels is not significantly larger than the real volume of the obstacle. A potential solution involves the use of deformable voxels, which can more accurately conform to the surfaces of real obstacles. Another possible approach is to use adaptive voxel sizing, where the voxel size is reduced near the surfaces of actual obstacles to enhance detail. However, both approaches have drawbacks, including complex implementation and an inconsistent number of voxels in the voxel map, which requires a more sophisticated data storage structure [29], [32]. The presented study introduces a fixed-grid voxelization method for point clouds, focused on minimizing the representation error of the actual volume and eliminating the swelling effect.

The current article is organized as follows: In Section II, the problem of convectional fixed grid point cloud voxelization and our novel fixed grid point cloud voxelization method are presented. Section III outlines the experimental validation of our method and its comparison with the standard voxelization method. The experimental setup, hypothesis, and results are described. In Section IV, the experiments and results are discussed and critically analyzed. Finally, Section V offers a conclusion of the study, as well as future directions for research.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section describes the definition of the problem that occurs when voxelizing a point cloud into a fixed voxel grid. In addition, the implementation of our proposed fixed grid voxelization method is described.

A. FIXED GRID VOXELIZATION

The basic voxelization pipeline is described by Algorithm 1. The first step is to create an empty voxel grid – all voxels are initialized with *occupied* = false and *pointCount* = 0. In the case of using an indexed voxel map structure, the grid is defined by its position relative to the robot coordinate system (vector variable *gridOrigin*) and the size (dimensions) of the grid bounding box. Based on the chosen voxel size, the space is divided into individual cells representing voxels (the number of cells along each coordinate axis is represented by

the integer vector variable *cellCount*). Then, the algorithm iterates through each point in the point cloud and uses the position of the point in space (vector variable *point*) to determine to which voxel the point belongs to. Any voxel that contains at least one point is classified as occupied. The listing in Algorithm 1 shows one of many possible ways of calculating the unique voxel identification integer number *voxelIndex*.

Algorithm 1 Voxelization

```

voxels = []
for point in pointCloud:
    index.x = floor((point.x - gridOrigin.x) / voxelSize)
    index.y = floor((point.y - gridOrigin.y) / voxelSize)
    index.z = floor((point.z - gridOrigin.z) / voxelSize)
    voxelIndex = index.x + index.y * cellCount.x +
                index.z * cellCount.x * cellCount.y
    voxels[voxelIndex].occupied = true
    voxels[voxelIndex].pointCount++
    
```

B. INACCURATE REPRESENTATION OF THE TRUE SHAPE

Voxels are a rough and simplified representation of an object, and the resulting voxel map always exceeds the shape of the actual object. This phenomenon is most noticeable when the edge of the sensed object is near the boundary between voxels in the grid. Noise in the data can even accentuate the problem – this situation is illustrated in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. The depth sensor (blue rectangle) senses an object (yellow rectangle) in the workspace. The actual point cloud (blue dots) oscillates near the surface of the object during sensing. The voxel grid (grey squares) is occupied by individual point cloud points. The voxelized object is expressed by the occupied voxels (green squares).

The presented voxelization method aims to minimize the representation error of the real object when voxelizing into a fixed voxel grid and to achieve the result illustrated in Figure 2.

In a previous paper [7], the authors used a control based on tracking the occupancy density of the point cloud voxel to eliminate this problem. The maximum possible density of points representing a voxel is variable based on the distance from the RGB-D sensor. If the actual voxel occupancy is less than the density coverage with a certain threshold, the voxel is considered unoccupied. The problem with this approach arises when we require, for example, 60% occupancy of the

FIGURE 2. The desired representation of the object (yellow rectangle) using voxels (green squares).

maximum density. In specific cases, the occupancy density may be split into two voxels with 50% and 50% occupancy, resulting in an unoccupied voxel grid.

C. PRESENTED SMART VOXELIZATION METHOD

In order to solve the above problem, we propose a new method for voxelizing a point cloud into a fixed grid. The method works as follows. First, the voxel grid is defined – the sensed space is divided into fixed voxels with a predefined voxel size. The depth sensor provides a depth image, which is then projected into a 3D space to obtain a point cloud. Each point corresponds to a specific pixel in the depth image. The depth image is a two-dimensional array for which it is easy to find a neighbouring point in the *x* and *y* direction. Based on that, it is possible to directly identify neighbouring points in the point cloud. Neighbouring points are connected into triangles to obtain a triangular mesh, as illustrated in Figure 3.

FIGURE 3. Triangular mesh, where the point cloud points (blue dots) form the vertices of triangles based on the depth image, which represents 2.5D data. The *x* and *y* coordinates of each pixel in the depth image and the *z* coordinate after projecting the point (pixel) into a 3D space are known. The triangle mesh is formed using the known neighbour relationships of the points based on their position in the depth image.

The normal of each triangle is calculated. For a triangle *t*₁, with vertices *V*₁, *V*₂, *V*₃, the normal is defined as:

$$\vec{n}_1 = \frac{(V_1 - V_2) \times (V_1 - V_3)}{\|(V_1 - V_2) \times (V_1 - V_3)\|} \tag{1}$$

If the triangles *t*₀, *t*₁, . . . , *t*_{*n*} share the vertex *V*_{*i*}, then the normal at vertex *V*_{*i*} is defined as:

$$\vec{n}_{V_i} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n \vec{n}_i}{\left\| \sum_{i=0}^n \vec{n}_i \right\|} \tag{2}$$

The voxel occupancy is determined based on our proposed method: For each point in the point cloud, we first determine its source voxel by the standard fixed voxelization (Algorithm 1). Each voxel has 26 neighbouring (orthogonally or diagonally adjacent) voxels, and we can choose one of them instead of the source voxel if there is a potential of more accurately representing the real sensed volume of the object. The source voxel to which the point was originally assigned is divided into octants; see Figure 4. It is determined in what octant the point is located, and only the neighbouring voxels that touch this octant are considered in the following steps. This reduces the number of potentially better neighbouring voxels from 26 to 7 by discarding voxels that are further away from the point.

FIGURE 4. 2D representation of defining potential voxels for assigning a point, the point (blue dot) is located in the bottom left part of the voxel (yellow square). Potential voxels that may more accurately represent the real object volume are coloured green.

The final voxel occupancy by the point is determined by an algorithm that compares the normal vector of the point, calculated from the triangular mesh, with the normalised directional vectors from the point to the centroids of the considered neighbouring voxels. The goal of this algorithm is to move voxels that cause a large overlap of the real object along the shortest possible path to the interior of the object. A model example of the proposed algorithm is shown in Figure 5. First, the directional vectors $\vec{d}_1, \vec{d}_2, \vec{d}_3, \vec{d}_4$ are calculated. The algorithm searches for the vector \vec{d}_i for which the value $\vec{d}_i \cdot \vec{n}_{V_i}$ is closest to -1 . This value indicates that the direction of vector \vec{d}_i is exactly opposite to the direction of the normal vector \vec{n}_{V_i} , which ensures a direct displacement into the object. In this particular example (Figure 5), it is the value of the dot product of the normal vector \vec{n}_{V_i} with the vector \vec{d}_4 . Therefore, the voxel to which the vector \vec{d}_4 points will be occupied.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

Experimental validation of our voxelization method was performed. The aim of the experiment was to com-

FIGURE 5. 2D representation of the point to voxel assignment algorithm – $\vec{d}_1 \dots \vec{d}_4$ are directional vectors from the point (blue dot) to voxel centroids (black dots); \vec{n}_{V_i} is the normal vector of the point according to the triangular mesh surface (black dashed line); green square represents the resulting occupied voxel.

pare the efficiency of our method with the standard method of voxelizing a point cloud into a fixed grid, when deployed in a robot obstacle avoidance system. First, the research experiment and hypotheses are defined, and then the results of the experiment are presented.

A. EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

The design of the experiment is based on a model scenario that can occur in workplaces with collaborative robots. A collaborative robot moves between defined positions *A* and *B*. When an obstacle is placed on the robot path, a path replanner proposes an alternative path, as illustrated in Figure 6. An important goal in designing a successful robotic application is to minimize the duration of the robot duty cycle time. If we can represent the obstacle more accurately using voxels, this can have a positive effect on the length of the replanned path.

FIGURE 6. Model scenario of an obstacle in the robot path. The depth camera captures the obstacle (yellow rectangle), which is represented by voxels (green squares). The path re-planner proposes an alternative path (red line) to the original path (blue line).

The aim of this experiment is to compare the effectiveness of the proposed voxelization method with the conventional method of voxelizing point clouds into fixed grids for generating alternative paths using a robot path re-planning solver. The effectiveness is determined by the voxel maps, which provide input information for the solver. The same point cloud was always voxelized using our method and using the conventional method. The objective parameter measured for comparison was the length of the alternative

path. Advanced voxelization methods could also be used for comparison, but methods such as adaptive voxelization or deformable voxels provide a different and more complex output data structure, which we wanted to avoid during the experiment.

Robot path replanning is not solved in this research, so the quality of the path planner should not affect the experimental verification. Thus, we use a simulated ideal path planner that always finds the shortest possible path around the voxels (touching the edges of the voxels, as demonstrated in Figure 6).

We fully acknowledge that our method, unlike the conventional method, may result in incomplete inclusion of parts of the scanned volume – the voxel surface may be up to half the voxel size (in the most extreme case) further behind the real obstacle surface. To achieve a fair comparison of the methods and to fully cover the potential collisions that may arise with our method, a safety offset of half the voxel size for our method is set in the path planner, as shown in Figure 7. Thus, only when using the simulated path planner with voxels generated by our proposed method, the path planner treats each voxel as if its side were twice as large while keeping the same center position. This adds a disadvantage to our method, so it cannot be considered unfair when presenting advantages of our method.

FIGURE 7. Illustration of the safety offset of half the voxel size (dashed area) implemented in the path planner for our proposed method.

To ensure that the experiment covers a wide range of different situations that can occur in a real workplace, a comprehensive dataset of point clouds was created. An experimental stand, shown in Figure 8, was built to collect point clouds of objects. The key parameters of the equipment used in the experiment are specified in Table 1.

A depth camera, Intel RealSense D435i [33], is mounted on the stand. The camera can be positioned relative to the mounted obstacle, so that the *z* axis of the camera coordinate system always points to the center of the object. The camera on the stand can be placed at all distances from the object listed in Table 2. The sensed objects were a sphere with a diameter of 170 mm and a cube with an edge length of 170 mm, as shown in Figure 9.

Based on our experience with collaborative applications and the typical dimensions of workplaces with collaborative robots, the parameters of the dataset were specified. The

TABLE 1. Key parameters of equipment used for experiment.

Intel RealSense D435i	
Depth technology	Active stereoscopic
Ideal range	0.3 m to 3.0 m
Maximum depth output resolution	1280 × 720 px
Used depth output resolution	640 × 480 px
Depth accuracy	<2% at 2 m
Depth Field of View (FOV)	87° × 58°
HP OMEN Laptop 17	
Processor	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7700HQ
GPU	NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1070
Random Access Memory (RAM)	16 GB
Operation system	Windows 10 Pro Build 19045

FIGURE 8. Stand for collecting point clouds.

FIGURE 9. Measured objects – a sphere and a cube.

TABLE 2. Point cloud dataset collection variables.

Parameter	Range
Measured objects	sphere and cube
Distance from sensor to object	0.6 – 1.3 m (step 0.1 m)
Number of images per position	10

range of each parameter was chosen to cover the situations that can occur in real workplaces, as shown in Table 2. The distance of the object from the sensor is defined as the shortest distance between the origin of the camera coordinate system and the surface of the measured object. This distance has a direct impact on the noise level in the point cloud image.

Data collection was performed using a custom-built C++ application using the Intel RealSense SDK. After data collection, we had a total of 160 unique point clouds

TABLE 3. Voxel grid parameters.

Parameter	Range
Voxel size	0.02 m – 0.06 m (step 0.01 m)
Offset of the fixed voxel grid origin	0 m – voxel size (50 steps)

expressed in the camera coordinate system. Then, a set of pairs of voxel maps was created. To expand the voxel map dataset with respect to the number of point clouds, we performed voxelization with different input parameters. This was in order to check for different anomalies in the behaviour of our method when using different voxel sizes and positions of the origin of the fixed voxel grid relative to the object being sensed. Each point cloud was voxelized using five different voxel sizes. The offset of the fixed voxel grid relative to the camera position can have a huge impact on the results, as discussed earlier (Figure 1, Figure 2), therefore, we divided the voxel size into 50 equal steps and created 50 different variations of voxel maps by shifting the origin of the voxel grid in the direction of the z axis of the camera. This expanded our dataset to a total of 40,000 unique voxel map pairs (160 point clouds, times 5 voxel sizes, times 50 offsets) that were used as obstacles in the robots path. The parameters and their range are listed in Table 3.

The calculation of the alternative path was implemented in the custom C++ application. The original path of the robot was defined by two points, A and B , in the camera coordinate system, as illustrated in Figure 10. The positions of the points were defined so that the original path always intersected the captured object. The exact positions of the points are provided in Table 4.

FIGURE 10. Representation of the relative positions of points A and B with respect to the camera coordinate system, forming an original path (magenta dashed line) that intersects the object being imaged (blue sphere). The voxels represent the volume passed to the robot path re-planning solver, which finds the alternative obstacle avoidance path (cyan line).

B. HYPOTHESIS

The initial hypothesis assumes that our method of voxelizing the point cloud into a fixed grid should provide a more accurate representation of the sensed object for the path

TABLE 4. Positions of points defining the original robot path.

Coordinates	Point A	Point B
x	-0.150 m	0.150 m
y	0 m	0 m
z	0.02 m + distance of the object from the camera	

re-planning solver. The dependent measure (objectively dependent variable) was defined as the length of the alternative path proposed by the robot path re-planning solver. The independent objective variable was defined as the voxelization method:

- VM1: Standard fixed grid voxelization.
- VM2: Our fixed grid voxelization.

The voxel map obtained using our method is expected to represent the surface of the scanned objects with fewer errors. The main research hypothesis is defined as follows.

Main Hypothesis (MH): *Our method (VM2) of voxelizing the point cloud into a fixed grid provides a more efficient representation of the object surface compared to the conventional method (VM1), leading to the generation of shorter paths in the robot path re-planning algorithm.*

This hypothesis assumes that differences in the voxelization method have a direct impact on the length of the re-planned paths generated by the planner. The efficiency of volume representation may be a key factor in the planner's ability to propose shorter robot paths, which can lead to a faster robot duty cycle.

In addition to the main hypothesis, additional hypotheses are defined to test specific aspects of the main hypothesis and provide a further context for comparing our method (VM2) with the conventional method (VM1). Additional research hypotheses are defined as follows.

- **Additional Hypothesis (AH1):** *Our method (VM2) is more effective than the conventional method (VM1) at various levels of noise in the point cloud.*
- **Additional Hypothesis (AH2):** *Our method (VM2) is more effective than the conventional method (VM1) when using different voxel sizes.*
- **Additional Hypothesis (AH3):** *Our method (VM2) is more effective than the conventional method (VM1) when the origin of the voxelization grid varies relative to the position of the scanned object.*

C. RESULTS

The main research hypothesis (MH) states that the obstacle will be better represented using our method, resulting in a shorter alternative path for the robot. The lengths of the paths for both voxelization methods were measured and compared.

The additional hypothesis AH1 states that the efficiency of our method compared to the conventional method is higher independently of the noise levels in the point cloud. The amount of noise is proportional to the distance at which the object was sensed. Figure 11 shows that the average length of the proposed robot paths is noticeably shorter in the VM2 voxelization method than in the VM1 voxelization method.

The path length was shorter on average for all the distances at which the object was imaged. Paired two sample for means T-tests were performed to compare the mean lengths of the alternative paths of the conventional and our method, always at specific distances and for specific object. In total, 16 T-tests were performed. All T-tests showed that the average path lengths were statistically different $t(499) > 20$, $p < 0.001$. Therefore, the additional hypothesis AH1 was confirmed and the main research hypothesis was supported.

The additional hypothesis AH2 states that the efficiency of our method is higher compared to the classical method independently of the voxel size used. The graphs in Figure 12 show that the path length of the VM2 method was on average shorter than the VM1 method for all voxel sizes used. The differences between the path lengths increase proportionally to the voxel size chosen. Paired two sample for means T-tests were performed to compare the mean lengths of the alternative paths of the conventional and our method, always at specific distances, with specific voxel size and for a specific object. In total, 30 T-tests were performed. All T-tests showed that the average path lengths were statistically different $t(499) > 20$, $p < 0.001$ across all the voxel sizes used. Therefore, the additional hypothesis AH2 was confirmed and the main research hypothesis was supported.

The additional hypothesis AH3 states that the efficiency of our method is higher compared to the classical method independently of the position of the origin of the fixed voxel grid with respect to the object being imaged. The graphs in Figure 13 show that the path lengths change when the origin of the fixed grid is shifted. The path length of the VM2 method was always shorter or the same compared to the path length of the VM1 method. Therefore, the additional hypothesis AH3 was confirmed and the main research hypothesis was supported.

IV. DISCUSSION

To assess the effectiveness of the developed voxelization method, we analyze its behaviour on examples of imaged objects and compare it with the conventional method of voxelizing a point cloud into a fixed grid.

Evaluation of the results of the experiment indicates statistically significant evidence that confirms the main research hypothesis MH and the additional hypotheses AH1, AH2, and AH3. The results indicate that our proposed method achieves better results in terms of shorter avoidance paths, as our method is able to provide the solver with a more accurate representation of the obstacle. Based on the confirmed additional hypotheses, it can be stated that our method achieves stable results with varying voxel sizes, levels of noise in the point cloud, and positions of the fixed voxel grid origin. The average increase in the length of the alternative avoidance path compared to the theoretical shortest path around the object was 15.7 % for the conventional method and 8.6 % for the presented method. Generally, it can be said that the voxel map obtained by voxelizing the point cloud using the proposed method can

FIGURE 11. Absolute path length depending on the distance of the sensed obstacle from the camera (lower is better): (a) ball - voxel size 50 mm, (b) cube - voxel size 50 mm.

FIGURE 12. Absolute path length depending on the voxel size used (lower is better): (a) ball – distance 600 mm, (b) ball – distance 1000 mm, (c) ball – distance 1300 mm, (d) cube – distance 600 mm, (e) cube – distance 1000 mm, (f) cube – distance 1300 mm.

more effectively represent the actual surface of the sensed objects.

Our method was designed for robot obstacle avoidance applications. For these applications, it is crucial that the voxel representation accurately reflects the shape of the obstacle without unnecessary overlaps, and that the path replanning solver is not provided with false obstacles. This effect can also be achieved using deformable voxels [34]. However, computational operations with a set of deformable voxels are more time consuming, which is undesirable for obstacle avoidance applications. Our method modifies how a given point is assigned to a voxel rather than altering the shape or size of the voxel. Therefore, it cannot be considered a direct alternative to advanced voxelization methods instead, it could be combined with these advanced methods.

Based on the results of the experiment, it can be concluded that our method can provide more accurate input information

for the robot path replanning solver. This allows the solver to propose shorter alternative paths, thereby speeding up the robot’s work cycle. However, during the design and testing of the proposed voxelization method, it was found that for effective representation of smaller objects, the voxel size should be reduced to a fraction of the dimensions of the object, approximately 50 % of the smallest size of the object, to take full advantage of the algorithm.

The deployment of our method may encounter challenges with objects whose shape includes cavities. However, this is a general issue when scanning objects with cavities using depth sensors. Points in the point cloud near a cavity may form a triangle with a distorted normal vector, which is unsuitable for the algorithm that compares normalized directional vectors from points to voxel centroids. Consequently, the resulting voxel map of such a concave object may resemble a convex object more closely. However, in applications focused on

FIGURE 13. Absolute path length depending on the shift of the fixed grid origin relative to the sensed object (lower is better): (a) ball – distance 1000 mm, voxel size 50 mm, (b) cube – distance 1000 mm, voxel size 50 mm.

avoiding dynamic obstacles, it is not expected that the robot would navigate through complex cavities of objects. A potential solution could involve limiting the maximum edge length of triangles during their construction.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new method for voxelizing a point cloud from a real RGB-D sensor into a fixed voxel grid was introduced. The method aims to perform voxelization with minimal error to efficiently represent objects in a robot workplace. When this voxel map is subsequently used as input information for the solver to dynamically re-plan the robot path. By achieving a better and more accurate representation of objects in the work scene, the solver can generate shorter avoidance paths for the robot.

The proposed voxelization method divides the space around the robot into fixed voxels. A triangular mesh is created from the point cloud, with individual triangles formed by neighbouring points based on their positions in the depth image. The normals of these triangles are then calculated. Subsequently, classical voxelization into a fixed grid is performed. The potential voxels that can better represent individual points in the cloud are then defined. Using an algorithm that works with the normals of the triangles, the occupancy of the voxel grid is adjusted so that the voxels more accurately represent the real sensed volume.

An experimental study was conducted to compare our proposed voxelization method with the classical method of

voxelization into a fixed grid. The comparison focused on the efficiency of representing the actual object with the voxel map. Objects at various distances were sensed using a depth sensor in an experimental setup. The resulting point clouds were then voxelized using both methods. The resulting voxel maps were used as obstacles in a predefined robot path. The final comparison of the methods was based on the comparison of the lengths of the avoidance paths generated by a simple robot path re-planning solver.

It was found that our voxelization method provided voxel maps that enabled the solver to propose shorter, collision-free avoidance paths around objects. This can lead to a faster robot working cycle time. The partial results of the experiment demonstrated that the proposed method consistently achieved better results across varying voxel sizes, levels of noise in the point cloud, and the position of the object relative to the origin of the voxel grid.

Future research will focus on further developing the proposed method, particularly on adapting the algorithm for voxelizing point clouds obtained from multiple RGB-D sensors. We see potential to enhance the proposed method by combining it with techniques based on statistical outlier removal or advanced non-fixed grid voxelization methods.

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